

The Unfairness of Popularity Bias in Book Recommendation. A Valuation of the Results of Naghiaei, Rahmani and Dehghan

Popularity Bias in Book Recommendations

Reevaluating Results: A Statistical Validation of the Paper “The Unfairness of Popularity Bias in Book Recommendation” from Naghiaei, Rahmani, and Dehghan's.

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Popularity bias represents a substantial challenge across various domains, influencing recommendation systems and the equitable promotion of popular and niche items. This study seeks to validate and replicate the findings of Naghiaei et al., who conducted a comprehensive investigation into population bias within book recommendation systems. Employing the Book-Crossing dataset and following Naghiaei et al.'s methodology, we categorized users into Niche, Diverse, and BestSeller-Oriented groups. Research Question 1 (RQ1) examined correlations between user profile size and engagement with popular books, while Research Question 2 (RQ2) evaluated state-of-the-art book recommendation algorithms, treating the problem as a rating prediction task. The study involved 30 iterations to address potential variability. The replication of RQ1 affirmed positive correlations between user profile size and engagement with popular books, consistent with Naghiaei et al.'s findings. RQ2 results revealed that 66% of datasets aligned with the original study, while 33% exhibited significant differences, indicating nuanced conditions. The BestSeller group consistently received superior recommendations across algorithms, emphasizing the persistence of popularity bias. However, the variation in significance across algorithms suggested a complex interplay between recommendation models and user preferences. This replication study contributes to the understanding of population bias in book recommendation systems. While affirming certain trends, it reveals that nuanced conditions impact the performance of recommendation algorithms.

Additional Keywords and Phrases: Recommender systems, Book recommendation, Popularity bias, Reproducibility

1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 Population bias in recommendation systems

In the realm of recommendation systems, population bias remains a persistent challenge. A study conducted by Naghiaei et al defines this challenge as follows: “Popularity bias refers to the problem that popular items (i.e., frequently rated items) are recommended frequently while less popular items are recommended rarely or not at all.” This characterization of the problem draws attention to the prevalence of frequently rated items, in recommendations, often sidelining content that is less popular or niche in nature. Achieving an equilibrium between popularity and personalization is challenging, as an excessive inclination toward popularity bias can result in a lack of niche content. Conversely, an extreme focus on personalization may lead to recommendations that are overfitted, potentially limiting users’ exposure to new and diverse items. Despite the availability of sophisticated algorithms, these factors make it difficult to devise a universally applicable solution. Moreover, the intricacies of user behavior and evolving preferences as well as the context of the domain further complicates the issue. As a result, the dynamic nature of user interactions paired with domain-specific intricacies continues to make population bias a pertinent issue in recommendation systems. However, handling the popularity bias and achieving the optimal balance is critical for enhancing the user experiences and creating a landscape that is both inclusive and reflective of individual preferences. [1]

1.2 Methodology of Naghiaei, Rahmani and Dehghan

The authors employed the well-known Book-Crossing dataset in their study on popularity bias in book recommendation systems. They started by preprocessing the dataset, removing implicit ratings and users with fewer than 5 ratings to focus on those likely to have rated enough long-tail items. This step aimed to create a fitting dataset for examining the bias towards popular items. They used the redefined dataset to address two research Questions.

RQ1: How much are different individuals or groups of users interested in popular books?

RQ2: How does the popularity bias in recommendation algorithms impact users with different tendencies toward popular books.

To address RQ1 the authors categorized users into three subgroups, namely Niche, Diverse and Bestseller-Oriented, based on the popularity of items in their profiles. They then investigated the correlation between users’ profile size and the number of popular items in their profiles, as well as the correlation between profile size and the average popularity of items. RQ2 was approached by studying state-of-the-art book recommendation algorithms, treating the problem as a rating prediction task with the evaluation setup for these algorithms remained consistent for fair comparison. The authors first conducted an analysis of the overall performance, irrespective of their performance for specific user groups or their tendencies towards popular items. Subsequently, an examination of popularity bias effects on distinct user groups within book recommendation. To quantify the unfairness of popularity bias, the delta Group Average Popularity metric was employed. In addition, various metrics were utilized, including Mean Absolute Error (MAE), Precision, Recall, and Normalized Discounted Cumulative Gain (NDCG). These metrics were applied to assess the performance of each recommendation algorithm across the user groups. Further statistical analyses were performed to determine significant differences, using a two-tailed paired t-test at a 95% confidence interval. The aim of this evaluation was to explore potential correlations between unfairness and popularity bias and personalization, assessed through NDCG. [1]

1.3 Findings of Naghiaei, Rahmani and Dehghan

Findings RQ1

The authors found a positive correlation between profile size and number of popular books in profile, and a negative correlation between profile size and average popularity of the books in the profile. That means, users with bigger profiles read more popular books than smaller ones and users with smaller profiles tend to have the biggest popular book ratio (they focus more and popular books than non-popular books). They also found that 83% of users have at least 20% unpopular books in their profile. The Diverse group has the biggest average profile size, then comes the Niche group and then the bestseller group. [1]

Findings RQ2

Due to the correlation finding, the authors expect the bestseller group to receive the highest quality predictions and the Niche group to receive the lowest quality predictions (since they are much less interested in popular books). The authors found out that the Niche group received the worst recommendations, then comes the Diverse group and the best recommendations are given for the bestseller-focused group. That matches their prediction made from the RQ1 findings. So, the authors conclude that the given algorithms are not capable to adapt the predictions to the user group. The WMF and VAECF algorithms are the ones that performed the best (in terms of accuracy) across all groups. [1]

2 REPRODUCING THE EXPERIMENTS

In the following sections focus on the performed reproduction steps of both research questions and possible additional tests. Since the authors provided the code in form of a jupyter notebook and the used dataset (via Github), we are reusing them for our reproduction steps.

2.1 Methodology & Results RQ1

The authors answered RQ1 by simply exploring the given data. Hence, the jupyter notebook cells for this research question were simply rerun and the outputs compared. No randomness should influence the data exploration steps in the notebook for this research question. The seed at the start of the notebook got changed to multiple values (default: 0, changed to: 1, 100, 1000) to check for any hidden randomness. For the default seed and the 3 proposed seeds all jupyter notebook cells which are important for this research question displayed the same outputs. The exact same findings as the authors described in 1.3 are reproduced for research question 1.

2.2 Methodology & Results RQ2

To replicate and validate the findings of RQ2, we ran the provided jupyter notebook. Since there is randomness involved in several notebook cells, 30 iterations were performed. Each iteration was executed with a distinct seed value, with the iteration number 30 chosen based on established norms for representational validity. The final code block of the notebook was adapted to output not only the graphical representation but also the raw values. The data was consolidated into four CSV files, delineating the validation performance metrics: Precision, MAE, Recall, and NDCG. Each file contains a 32x27 matrix of values, where the first row represents the values found in the original study. The columns correspond to the performance of different recommendation approaches, segmented by niche, diverse, or bestseller categories across various machine learning algorithms: MostPop, BPR, MF, PMF, NMF, WMF, PF, NeuMF, and VAECF. The datasets were subjected to the Shapiro-Wilk test to determine if they follow a normal distribution, which is assumed for p-values greater

than 0.05. Subsequently, a Z-test was applied to the normally distributed (ND) data to ascertain whether the values from the paper significantly deviate from the ND data. For the non-normally distributed data, the non-parametric Wilcoxon signed-rank test was employed. The Wilcoxon test is appropriate in this context as it does not assume data normality, making it suitable for comparing the data of paper to the median of the sample. Additionally, their final diagram got reproduced with the means of the 30 iterations. The results can be seen in figure 1. The results depicted in the flowchart provide a picture of the statistical validation process applied to the study. The initial Shapiro-Wilk tests were conducted on 108 datasets to assess normality, with 85 datasets (79%) being classified as normally distributed (ND) and 23 datasets (21%) as not normally distributed (Not ND). For the ND datasets, a Z-Test was performed, where 58 (68%) showed no significant difference from the original results, suggesting that the majority of the ND datasets align with the findings of Naghiaei et al. In contrast, 27 (32%) indicated a significant difference, signaling potential variations from the initial study's results. For the Not ND datasets, the non-parametric Wilcoxon test was used. The outcomes revealed that 14 (61%) of these datasets did not significantly differ from the original study, whereas 9 (39%) did show a significant difference.

Figure 1 A flowchart showing the results of the Shapiro-Wilk tests with subsequent Z-Test and Wilcoxon test outcomes.

To provide a comprehensive valuation of whether the results significantly differ, we calculate a weighted average of the "Not Significant different" (Formula 1) and "Significant different" (Formula 2) categories across both ND and Not ND datasets.

$$Weighted\ Average_{Not\ sig.} = \left(\frac{58}{108}\right) + \left(\frac{14}{108}\right) = 0.66 \quad (1)$$

$$Weighted\ Average_{sig.} = \left(\frac{27}{108}\right) + \left(\frac{9}{108}\right) = 0.33 \quad (2)$$

The given weighted averages suggest that 66% of the datasets did not show a significant difference from the original study results, while 33% did.

Figure 2: Comparison of results (left: results of authors, right: reproduced results)

Upon comparing the heatmaps generated from our iterations with the original study, it is evident that the significance varies slightly for each run and each algorithm. While a consistent trend emerges across all iterations, indicating that the BestSeller group consistently receives the best results, it is important to note that the specific algorithms driving this preference may fluctuate between iterations.

3 DISCUSSION OF THE RESULTS

3.1 Interpretation of the Results

The replication of the first research question showed no deviations of the output from the output presented by the authors. Hence the findings for RQ1 can be successfully reproduced with the given resources. The replication attempts for RQ2 revealed that 66% of the datasets did not show a significant deviation from the original findings. This substantial proportion suggests a general alignment with the original study, reinforcing the validity of its conclusions in the field of book recommendation systems. However, the 33% of datasets that did exhibit significant differences cannot be overlooked. These variations indicate that while the overall trends of the original study hold, there are conditions under which the findings might diverge. This could be attributed to the inherent variability in machine learning model performances or differences in book categories, suggesting a more nuanced interpretation of the original study's results.

The heatmap computed via the means of the 30 iterations shows small variations to the heatmap generated by the authors. However, we are still able to reproduce their conclusion, which was that the Bestseller group got the best recommendations, and the Niche group got the worst recommendations, hence the given algorithms are not capable of adapting to different user groups. Their second finding to this question (WMF and VAECF did the best) was also reproduced with our heatmap.

Appendix

Code/Setup Difficulties	
Code not provided	Code provided (via Github)
Code partially not provided	Code provided
Faulty code provided	99% works (just one cell for debugging purposes malfunctions)
Information about software versions missing	Only python import statements given
Specific hardware and software setup necessary	Not if run via provided Google Collab notebook
Data	
Data not provided	Data provided (via Github)
Data partially not provided	Data provided
Metadata not provided	~via Github README
Process	
Comparison metrics or baselines not discussed	Baselines discussed (Random & MostPop)
Experimental setup not described	Experimental setup described
Experiment workflow incomplete	Experimental workflow complete
Inconsistencies in paper, code and data	No inconsistencies in provided code and described results
Results differ significantly	Data for RQ2 differs from performed reproduction experiment

REFERENCES

- [1] Naghiaei, Mohammadmehdi, Hossein A. Rahmani, and Mahdi Dehghan. "The unfairness of popularity bias in book recommendation." *International Workshop on Algorithmic Bias in Search and Recommendation*. Cham: Springer International Publishing, 2022